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A Model Study on Early Music Education (Ages 0-5) in Türkiye: *The Heart Notes*¹

Türkiye’de Erken Dönem Müzik Eğitimi (0-5 Yaş) Üzerine Model Bir İnceleme:

Kalpli Notalar

ABSTRACT

Early childhood is a period that requires comprehensive support for children to reach their maximum potential, when brain development is at its peak. Studies on brain development in early childhood reveal significant neural growth in sensory areas related to vision, hearing, motor skills, and language skills. In particular, incorporating physical activities, strengthening and developing them, offers lasting benefits for brain health. Consequently, any learning or activity that is neurologically supported is thought to strengthen synaptic connections, thereby enhancing cognitive function and supporting overall brain health. The interaction between music and brain development in early childhood has become particularly evident following the increase in music programs in education. For children, participation in music education, particularly through instrumental training, increases the activation of brain regions responsible for movement control. Beginning instrumental training at an early age accelerates motor-sensory integration by enhancing the growth of the corpus callosum, the structure encompassing the two hemispheres of the brain. This development not only improves physical coordination but also supports higher-level functions such as executive functions and attention management. The primary goal of developing a program with guidelines suitable for infants and preschoolers in Türkiye, applicable both in music workshops and at home, is to ensure that interaction with auditory, sensory, and visual stimuli is beneficial and enjoyable. This music initiative aims to develop children's cultural identities and language skills by incorporating traditional Turkish musical rhythms, folk melodies, and lullabies.

Keywords: Education, Early Childhood, Music, Development.

ÖZET

Erken çocukluk dönemi, çocuğun beyin gelişiminin en yüksek olduğu maksimum potansiyellerine ulaşmaları için kapsamlı destek gerektiren bir dönemdir. Erken çocukluk döneminde beyin gelişimi üzerine yapılan çalışmalar, görme, işitme, motor beceriler ve dil yeteneğiyle ilgili duyuşsal alanlardaki sinirsel büyümede belirgin bir büyüme ortaya çıkmaktadır. Özellikle, fiziksel aktivitelerin bir araya getirilmesiyle, güçlendirerek, geliştirilerek ve beyin sağlığı için kalıcı faydalar sunulmaktadır. Bu duruma bağlı olarak, sinirsel olarak desteklenerek herhangi bir öğrenim veya aktivitenin sinaptik bağlantıları güçlendirdiği, böylece bilişsel işlevi artırdığı ve genel beyin sağlığını desteklediği düşünülmektedir. Erken çocukluk döneminde müzik ve beyin gelişimi arasındaki etkileşim, özellikle eğitim alanındaki müzik programlarında olan artışların ardından ortaya çıkmıştır. Müzik eğitiminde çocuklar için, özellikle enstrüman eğitimi yoluyla katılım, hareket kontrolünden sorumlu beyin bölgelerinin aktivasyonunu artırır. Enstrüman eğitimine erken yaşta başlayarak, beynin iki yarım küresini kapsayan yapı olan korpus kallozumunun büyütülmesini artırarak motor-duyuşsal bütünleşmeyi hızlandırmaktadır. Bu gelişme yalnızca fiziksel koordinasyonu geliştirmekle kalmaz, aynı zamanda yönetimsel faaliyetler ve dikkat yönetimi gibi üst düzey hizmetlerin de sürdürülmektedir. Türkiye’de bebekler ve okul öncesi çocuklara uygun hem müzik atölyelerinde hem de ev ortamında uygulanabilen kılavuzlara sahip bir program geliştirmenin temel amacı, işitsel, duyuşsal ve görsel uyaranlarla etkileşimin faydalı ve keyifli olmasını sağlamaktır. Bu müzik girişimi, geleneksel Türk müzik ritimlerini, halk ezgilerini ve ninnilerin dâhil edilmesiyle çocukların kültürel kimliklerini ve dil becerilerini geliştirmeyi amaçlamaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Eğitim, Erken Çocukluk Dönemi, Müzik, Gelişim.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Early childhood is a critical period when the brain's plasticity peaks, requiring comprehensive support to fully realize its potential. Brain development during early childhood exhibits significant neuroplasticity in sensory areas related to vision, hearing, motor skills, and language skills. For example, some studies have highlighted the benefits of music education for children's brain development, showing that it can increase neuroplasticity in the frontoparietal lobe, improve cognitive abilities such as attention, memory, and auditory processing, and strengthen neural connections (Vance et al., 2010).

Music plays a vital role in people's lives. As children grow, they encounter music in every aspect of their lives and interact with it in various ways. Whether through games, nursery rhymes, or songs on television, they integrate music into their daily lives. Educators and parents should be aware of the impact of music on child development. Music, an important art form, has always been an indispensable experience throughout human history. Many people have sought to express themselves more effectively through sound, communicate their intentions, and achieve spiritual fulfillment (Çadır & Avcıoğlu, 2013).

Early childhood music education is a multifaceted educational experience that supports children's cognitive, social, and emotional development. Therefore, creating a well-structured and rich musical environment from early childhood is crucial for providing children with more effective and lasting learning opportunities. The involvement of educators and families is essential for maximizing a child's potential. Music, nursery rhymes, and songs have a significant and positive impact on early childhood development (Soysal, 2012).

This article focuses on the importance of early music education for children aged 0-5 in Türkiye. The primary objective of the study is to develop a practical music education model specific to this age group and to clarify Türkiye's educational policies and practices in this area. The findings will provide valuable guidance for educators and families, support the musical development of infants and toddlers, and encourage widespread acceptance and implementation of early music education throughout society.

1.1 The Importance and Impact of Early Years Music Education

In early childhood education, music plays a vital role in children's social and personality development. Children are constantly surrounded by a wide variety of sounds and tones and interact with music in various ways. They participate in a variety of activities, including listening to and recognizing sounds, vocalization and breathing, rhythm, singing, creative dance, musical theater performances, and storytelling with music. These experiences allow them to express their emotions through music and develop their creativity. While some children are naturally interested in and talented at music, it's important to understand that everyone's musical abilities vary.

The goal of early childhood music education is to support children's emotional, cognitive, linguistic, and psychomotor development. This means enabling children to express their thoughts and feelings through rhythm and song, encouraging them to engage with musical culture, and fostering their passion for music. A child's musical environment can have either a positive or negative impact on their musical development. And the early childhood educational institution they attend has the greatest impact on children's musical development (Millî Eğitim Bakanlığı, 2007).

In the first few months after birth, babies respond to music, turning their heads toward the sound's source, experiencing its calming effect, and eventually falling asleep. These early responses often evolve into more pronounced ones, expressed through various movements and vocalizations, even if these movements and vocalizations are not synchronized with the music's rhythm. Over time, the initial passive listening phase gradually transitions to a phase of active participation (Ömeroğlu, Ersoy, Şahin, Kandır, & Turla, 2006). The first phase of instrument training should focus on infants between the ages of 0 and 2, after the mother becomes pregnant. It is recommended that musical education begin not only after birth but also after the child has successfully adapted to its environment. The primary goal for infants in this age group is to encourage them to explore the sounds of the instrument in all its high and low registers (Jackman, 2001).

1.2 Early Music Education Models in Turkey

Music education is recognized as an important resource for supporting children's cognitive, emotional, psychomotor, and social development. Furthermore, research shows that children who receive music education in early childhood are more likely to strengthen their social bonds and form healthy interpersonal relationships (Small, 1998).

Türkiye's music education policy aims to support children's artistic development while preserving and developing cultural values. The primary goals of music education initiatives developed by the Ministry of National Education are to make music a compulsory subject in formal education and to increase the accessibility of non-formal music education. However, these policies have not achieved the expected results, particularly in the non-formal education sector. The preschool education plan implemented by the Ministry of National Education in 2013 emphasizes the role of music as a tool in meeting children's developmental needs (Erdamar & Gündüz, 2015).

Music centers are educational spaces that develop children's musical knowledge and skills and provide them with valuable experiences. Establishing a music center in a kindergarten not only helps children develop their individual musical talents at an early age but also supports the development of a broader musical culture. Most importantly, the center must be equipped with appropriate instruments and tools that both teachers and children can use effectively to develop their sense of rhythm and auditory perception. Through the use of these instruments and equipment, children will have the opportunity to develop their cognitive, linguistic, motor, social, and emotional skills. It is also important for teachers to encourage children to create instruments and equipment that produce various sounds using recycled materials (Millî Eğitim Bakanlığı, 2013).

In Türkiye, public education centers (PECs) form the foundation of formal music education. These centers offer children and adolescents the opportunity to receive musical education. However, the effectiveness of these programs is often limited due to a lack of qualified teachers and resources. In large urban centers, informal music education programs offered by public education centers and local governments offer a broader and more diverse range of opportunities than in rural areas. This imbalance prevents formal education from reaching its full potential. According to Erdamar and Gündüz (2015), there is a lack of qualified teachers and educational materials in formal music education (Erdamar & Gündüz, 2015).

Involving children in musical activities through play ensures their enthusiastic and enjoyable participation. These activities allow children to release excess energy while having fun. When implemented correctly, these activities have many positive effects on child development. Children gain rich experiences through musical activities. Furthermore, careful observation during these activities can identify gifted children and create opportunities for them to develop their talents. Communication with parents can encourage these children to continue their music education beyond school.

Another limitation of Türkiye's music education policy is the lack of adequate support for teachers' professional development. Many music teachers lack professional knowledge, and in-service training programs designed to support their professional development are far from adequate (Yanmaz Düztaban, 2025).

1.3 International Early Music Education Models

Education cannot be successfully implemented with a single method. Numerous factors, including children's psychology, individual differences, the abilities of the group or individual being taught, the nature of the subject, teaching methods, and other factors, influence the effectiveness of education. Furthermore, specific teaching activities should be designed to engage multiple senses. For example, a teaching strategy that emphasizes visual elements to aid understanding of a topic may be more effective than a strategy that engages other senses, and vice versa. Furthermore, an individual's age and developmental stage are also important factors in curriculum development (Aylaz, 2018).

Pedagogy focuses on understanding the principles of mental functioning to increase teaching effectiveness; it aims to align with the mind's inherent characteristics and thereby promote more comprehensible learning. The primary goal of teaching methodologies is to determine how individuals interpret educational content, how they make sense of it, how they establish connections between different elements, and how to convey this knowledge most effectively to students.

Having sufficient musical knowledge and being able to effectively convey this knowledge to students are equally important. Clear and concise teaching methods are vital for supporting students' holistic development of musical literacy and ensuring healthy progress in music learning. Especially in one-on-one music lessons, teachers should analyze students' physiological structures, psychological characteristics, and mental states and develop personalized teaching plans accordingly; this is one of the most important skills for teachers (Yıldız, 2002). A wide variety of methods and techniques are used in music education. However, for this article, it is useful to examine some teaching methods currently

effective in preschool education. Some of the most important teaching methods are:

- Kodaly Teaching Method
- Orff Teaching Method
- Suzuki Teaching Method

The early childhood education curriculum encompasses a variety of musical activities, including listening to and identifying sounds and music, rhythm exercises, vocalization and breathing exercises, singing, playing musical instruments, creative movement and dance, musical movement, and creating musical stories. Teachers in early childhood education institutions have the important responsibility of implementing these curricula and instilling a love of music in children. At this critical stage of developing musical enlightenment and interest, careful planning and execution of musical activities are vital (Aylaz, 2018).

2. METHODS

2.1 Research Model

The New Model, implemented in registered regions across Türkiye for babies, ages 0-4 years and older, aims to complement previous free music education initiatives and extend their benefits to infants. This initiative is called "Heart Notes" and will be referred to by this name in the following discussions.

The "Heart Notes" educational framework aims to develop the musical perception of infants and young children aged 0-5, combining the universality and tradition of music with the ability to perceive subtle differences, developing and enriching their imaginations. This model has been designed and implemented in parent-child music workshops that I have personally led for the past four years.

When creating a music program with infants and preschoolers in Türkiye, our primary goal is to ensure that communication through auditory, visual, and tactile stimuli is both practical and comfortable, whether in music workshops or at home. In this context, the teacher's musical expertise and active delivery, along with interaction with frequency, melody, instructional modes, and emotional expression, are crucial for facilitating early observation of infants and toddlers. This music program includes traditional Turkish musical rhythms, folk songs, and lullabies, aiming to develop people's cultural identity and language skills.

2.2 Core Components of the Model

One of the fundamental components of the "Heart Notes" educational framework is developing the ability to keep a rhythm in activity. This skill is crucial for the musical education regimen because it significantly influences their perception of rhythm and pulse. Babies are aware of their mothers' heartbeats, and this naturally accompanies them to this ritual from birth. Gently tapping their knees or back while singing can significantly support vestibular system development, support language development, and enhance their sense of rhythm. The nerve cells developed in the brain during early childhood play a significant role in shaping children's therapeutic strategies, learning skills, and permanent vision impairments. Therefore, it has a significant impact on shaping users' lifelong experiences and musical development. Through active and enthusiastic participation in musical activities, dance, and games, they can experience truly meaningful and meaningful experiences.

Research shows that babies respond more strongly and at a higher level to music and its rhythmic properties than to spoken language. Observational studies show that children whose movements are regulated by music laugh more. Therefore, any sentence or song presented to music has a more direct impact on children than verbal communication and helps them develop more advanced imitation skills. Another important component of this model is observing and responding to infants' babbling. Infants' high and low notes are encouraging, and products and materials should be imitated and named appropriately. For example;

“- now a deep voice like a lion,”

“- now a thin voice like a bird.”

In some music activities, glissando (changing pitch from low to high or vice versa) is an effective exercise that helps children explore and expand their vocal range. The teacher needs to observe whether the children participate in their singing, whether they sing in the correct pitch and with appropriate lyrics,

and to praise and encourage their performance. For example;

“- DO-MI, come on, you tell me now?”

“- Yes, it's great, you chose to sing "Do" with a deeper voice, isn't "MI" higher?”

Play should be the cornerstone of music education, as children acquire the characteristics of music most effectively through play. Encouraging musical games and activities that include improvisation within the curriculum is crucial. Incorporating rhythmic songs into "colorful parachute" games and aligning movements to the rhythm (such as ascent and descent, changes in speed, wave-like movements, and balance) is becoming an increasingly effective strategy. Furthermore, parachute-related movements can stimulate the growth vestibular system and the balance coordination center.

Because acoustic music plays a vital role in babies' auditory and cognitive development, teachers must have instrumental skills. Instruments that can produce a variety of sounds, such as the guitar, ukulele, piano, and baglama, are invaluable resources in this regard. Furthermore, instruments that can be combined with digital music, such as the flute, clarinet, and violin, provide auditory experiences with their rich timbres.

3. RESULTS

This study presents the effects of music education on infants aged 0-5 years during early development. It has positive effects on children's emotional and motor perceptions during this period. The effects of music education on infants in early childhood are discussed.

- **Rhyming Rhymes**

Parents and babies often sing rhymes using music. Rhythmic language, through learned rhythm, facilitates both singing and language development. For example, a baby may rise to the melody while saying "Now." They can simultaneously mirror the melody and rhythm employed by older children's collectives. Rhyming rhymes help children use vocal pitches, including highs, lows, and various other variations, in personal verbal communication. These experiences contribute to the development of children's reading and writing skills. Rhyming words help children learn language and phonological patterns.

- **Feeling the Pulse**

Children and their parents develop as they move to the rhythm. One of the fundamental elements of musical rhythm is the ability to create a strong pulse. Everyone has a sense of rhythm, stemming from the events that originate in the womb's hissing heartbeat. The emphasis in memory is not on "melody," but on "sense of rhythm," and includes movements such as rocking, popping, or the rotation of hands, arms, and feet. The perception of rhythmic movement will help facilitate the progression of the process and the acquisition of other knowledge, such as walking, jumping rope, running, and general motor skills.

- **Baby Massage Rhymes**

Physical contact is an important tool for fundamental learning in babies. Suitable for babies aged 0-12 months, this method combines short, rhythmic rhymes with the gentle touch of a caregiver. It helps babies communicate emotionally, especially with pacing, and develop their communication skills. As they observe, listen, and respond to their babies' messages, the fundamental ambiguities of communication begin to emerge. This communication also helps strengthen the parent-child bond. Babies also begin to understand words for body parts such as nose, toes, and mouth, and basic concepts such as up and down—all of which are language limitations.

- **Floor and Chair Games**

Activation of the vestibular system is a critical stage in infant and toddler development. Movement helps strengthen a cohesive rhythm or pulse. Working spatially and moving in different planes, including vertical movements (up and down), plays a vital role in sensory integration and spatial information processing in children.

- **Group Dance**

These activities, such as dancing or being held by parents, can activate the vestibular system. By participating in group dances, they can foster a sense of community and develop socially. Babies are introduced to a wide variety of expressions, forms, rhythms, and melodies. Lullabies, especially sung at the end of activities, can help soothe the mind and skin and strengthen parent-child bonds. In addition to traditional lullabies, lullabies from different cultures will be selected to enrich the intercultural musical experience. This approach can strengthen interpersonal bonds and support emotional development. Swaying to music can also activate the vestibular system.

Introducing babies to universals offers valuable learning opportunities by helping them identify, differentiate, and select different cultural expressions. In the early stages, it's recommended to use only one instrument. A single sound is more beneficial than multiple sounds at once. Around four months of age, babies begin to understand and master musical instruments, rattles, or other instruments.

As part of the Heart Song program, babies should be provided with safe instruments and encouraged to sing. As part of the "Hearty Notes" program, free episodes feature music from a variety of cultures. Consequently, children will not perceive opera as foreign when they encounter it in the future; rather, they will recognize their previous exposure to genres like jazz, blues, Latin, or classical music.

- **Sample Lesson Plans That Can Be Applied in Early Music Education**

While parental involvement is important for babies, it's also recommended that they have a trusted adult around when their parents aren't around. Babies have very limited attention spans, so songs should be designed for repetition. The "Heart Notes" curriculum, specifically designed for babies aged 12 to 36 months, uses a variety of instruments, including cymbals, xylophones, triangles, and drums that make sounds when struck or shaken. Regular repetition of curriculum content is crucial for babies to recognize and understand the different parts of the curriculum and, ultimately, to establish the meaning of the song.

- At the beginning of each lesson, sit in a circle on the floor and sing "Hello." This initial activity will help babies establish rapport and increase their group awareness.
- The opening verse of the "Hello" song is a greeting to the entire class and the day ahead. In the second part, each child is individually addressed by name, invited to interact with the instrument being played, and encouraged to create rhythms using their index fingers.
- Following the "Hello" song, babies are allowed to interact with a single instrument. This approach allows them to play 3-4 songs on a single instrument, while also allowing for one or two songs to be played freely, allowing them to explore and try all the available instruments.
- It would be beneficial to include songs in different languages and rhythms, in addition to Turkish songs, and it is recommended that you share this playlist with parents.
- Although it may be challenging at first, babies need to get into the habit of saying "goodbye" to their instrument after each song and returning it to the box designated by the teacher. This practice not only boosts motivation for the next activity but also helps them understand the transitions between endings and beginnings, thus maintaining order in the classroom.
- Group dances and collective movements are recommended at the end of the lesson. In this context, sturdy, mobile materials such as tulle and parachutes will be beneficial in developing the child's spatial awareness and vestibular system.
- Listening to a short lullaby at the end of each lesson provides a delightful opportunity for parents to strengthen their bond with their babies.
- Lessons conclude with the "Goodbye" song, signaling the end of the music lesson. This familiar melody encourages the child to leave the room feeling inspired for the upcoming lesson.

– Table 1. Sample Lesson Plan - 1

Activity	Name	Explanations	Vehicles
Forming a circle and greeting each other	Hello song	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Everyone beats their knees to the song. • The song, directed at each name, is repeated, and the baby is approached and asked to touch the instrument. • At the end of the song, play a little "high-low" game. For the low-low sound, hit their belly and yell "OOO!", while for the high-low sound, hit their head and say "Tsk-Tsk" like a bird. This helps babies recognize where the high and low sounds are directed. 	Ukulele, Guitar, Keyboard etc.
Music and Movement	Shake Shake	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sing the song together, following the movement instructions. During the "Shake Up" part, the voice is lowered by doing a glissando. During the "Shake Down" part, it is lowered. • <u>Turning - Continue swinging by hitting the ground.</u> 	Bell ribbons
	We're Going to the Moon!	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Babies sit on their mothers' knees, and their knees are raised. • The baby's body is moved up and down with the knees, keeping time to the song. • The countdown is slowed down, and at the end, the baby is lifted into the air with the words "ZOOM." 	None
	Pull the Shovels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All the babies form a circle, hold the end of the elastic band, and swing it back and forth while singing the song. During the 'merry-merry' part, the elastic band is shaken quickly. 	Large rubber hoop
Massage Rhymes	Sounds of Nature (Just yesterday, our mother's)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The babies stand around the drum, the mothers behind them. A story is told as if they were in a forest. Suddenly, the arms raise to the air, saying, "Raindrops are falling from the very top," and the fingers land on the drum with a "pat-pat" sound. • They draw circles on the drum with their palms to simulate the sound of wind. • They make fists and beat "pat-pat" to make the sound of snow. All babies are encouraged to beat a steady rhythm, and they sing the song "Just yesterday, our mother." • At the end of the song, a small, safe object is taken out of a pocket and thrown into the center of the drum. • The babies speed up the rhythm, <u>imagining making the object dance.</u> 	Large ground drum
	Zig-zag Look at This	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Draw diagonal lines on the baby's back with your fingertips and sing the nursery rhyme "Zig-Zag Look at That." • Walk toward the baby's neck with two fingers for "The little ant climbed the tree." • <u>Blow on the baby's neck for "A warm breeze," ending with a tickle.</u> 	Plush toy for demo
Keeping the rhythm	Woodpecker song	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sticks are banged together throughout the song. Pay attention to the pauses in the "knock-knock-knock" part. • For young babies, the parent holds one stick and gives the other to the baby, observing them banging each other. 	Rhythm Sticks/Plush demo toy
Rhythmic Practice with Drums	Beat the Drum	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Each baby is given a small drum. • During the song, at the appropriate words, the drum is hit 3 times, and the sides are hit 3 times. 'Pat-pat-pat' • In up-down movements, the sticks are made as if they were being turned in the hand. • When becoming a rabbit, sticks are displayed on top of the head as if they were two ears. • 'When becoming a squirrel' Sticks are shown as if they have fallen in two. 	Small floor drum and rhythm sticks
Standing Movement	I Put the Chickpeas in the Bowl Ant Ms. Tiny	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The babies are given two tulle shawls. • They stand, form a circle, and the babies are held or held by their hands. • During the intro of the song, the tulle shawls swing rhythmically left and right, up and down. • They sway calmly in place. • When the song begins, they run sideways during the second verse of the song. • During the "hop" part, jump and walk into the circle 2-3-4-5 times. During the "come," jump and walk back 2-3-4-5 steps. • During the "A" part, the tulle hangs overhead. • During the "Brrrr" part, the tulle falls down, pretending to tremble. • During the chorus, the tulle shawls are swayed rhythmically. The song is repeated twice. • Some babies are given tambourines, while others are given maracas. • During the intro, everyone sways to the beats and continues walking. • In section A, pause on the 'tin-tin' parts and then continue to swing rhythmically. 	Colorful Tulle/Audio Music Instructor's Instrument Tambourine, Maracas
Note information	The World of Notes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The song is played acoustically. • Then, families are asked to "repeat after me." • During free time, a maximum of three notes are sung in succession (such as C-RE-MI). • Families repeat the notes in the same rhythm. • As the weeks progress, this section can be developed, and melodies can be created using all the notes. 	Colorful bells

Table 2. Sample Lesson Plan - 2

Activity	Name	Explanations	Vehicles
Playing Instruments	Pufito	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Babies love hearing their mother's voice. Give your ukulele or guitar to mom for this song. Have her play a simple string, like C Major. Sit baby across from mom and show her how to keep rhythm with one finger, from top to bottom, on the strings Encourage her to keep a steady rhythm and start singing the song with mom. Don't forget to mention the baby's name in the song! 	Ukulele, Guitar
	Clown	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Wait for the child to imitate your voice during the rest of the song. 'Come Out Clown' Praise and imitate when he/she makes a high/low sound. 	Hiding Clown toy
	Shake the Maracas	Babies are given maracas, and they are shaken and danced according to the song's instructions.	Maracas
Finger games	Tralala	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 'Bling Bling': The hands are fisted and opened forward. 'Tralala': The hands are waved forward. 'Fışfışfış': The hands are rubbed together. In the glissando section, the upper body is shifted to the right and left. 	Large rubber hoop
	Where are you, my thumb?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This traditional finger game will be very interesting for babies. According to the instructions in the song, babies point to various parts of their bodies with their fingers. 	
Free Songs	Selections from World Music	Babies and families accompany the music by choosing from the instruments distributed around.	All instruments for babies

Söz-müzik: Aylin Özer Tepe

Mer - ha - ba___ Mer ha ba___ Mer - ha - ba si - ze

7 Mü - zik do - lu bir gün - den mer - ha - ba si - ze

Figure 1. Notes of the Song Hello

The song is written in the key of C Major. The vocal range is one octave. The lesson is designed to facilitate opening, welcoming, and accompanying, and to begin the lesson with joy and motivation by adding the children's names one by one.

İngiliz ezgisi

Çek çek kü - rek - leri yüz - dür tek - ne - ni

5 ne - şe - li ne - şe - li ne - şe - li - ha - yat rü - ya gibi

Figure 2. Sheet Music for the Song Pull the Oars

The song is written in C major, with a 1-octave range. It can be accompanied by bowing back and forth in a 6/8 rhythm.

Müzik: Lynn Kleiner

Mü - zik zaman - ı Pu - fi - to mü - zik zama - nı pu - fi - to
Mer - haba (çocuğun ismi) Pu - fi - to mer - haba (çocuğun ismi) pu - fi - to

mü - zik zaman - ı pu - fi - to şar - kı - nı söy - le pu - fi - to
mer - haba (çocuğun ismi) pu - fi - to

zil - ler sal - la gül - eğ - len şar - kı - nı söy - le

13 Opsiyonel bitiş:
pu - fi - to pu - fi - to şar - kı - nı söy - le pu - fi - to

17 Önerilen Tekrarlar:
da - vul zaman - ı pu - fi - to da - vul zaman - ı pu - fi - to
mara - kas zaman - ı pu - fi - to mara - kas zaman - ı pu - fi - to
şim - di para - şüt pu - fi - to şim - di para - şüt pu - fi - to
para - şütü top - la pu - fi - to para - şütü top - la pu - fi - to
zil - leri top - la pu - fi - to zil - leri top - la pu - fi - to

Figure 3. Notes of the Pufito Song

The song is written in the key of C Major. Its vocal range is one octave. Its highest note is the high C, and it was composed to emphasize children's awareness of low and high notes. This song can encourage children to maintain a steady rhythm on instruments. It can also be used to signal changes in activities or meeting times during class.

(notaların el işaretleri yapılr) Söz-müzik: Aylin Özer Tepe

No - ta - la - nn dün - ya - sı çok renk - li - dir çok tat - lı do en ka - lın ses re o - nun üs - tün - de

mi dur - gun su gi - bi fa ör - değin ayak - lar - ı sol ör - değin kafa - sı

la ke - di ku - la - ğı si sivri si - nek gi - bi do yine ince do

do re mi fa sol la si do do si la sol fa mi re do

Figure 4. Sheet Music for the Song World of Notes

This song is in C Major, with a one-octave range. Its lowest note is High C. The song was written to raise children's awareness of note names and sounds, while also teaching them the notes using the hand signals used in the Kodaly Method.

4. CONCLUSION

Early childhood is considered a critical phase in an individual's cognitive, emotional, social, and motor development. The education provided during this period lays the foundation for an individual's lifelong learning process and ensures the maximum realization of their developmental potential. Music education stands out as an effective educational field that contributes to the multifaceted development of children aged 0-5. When examining current practices and policies in early music education in Turkey, the lack of a systematic and comprehensive approach in this area is striking.

The model proposed in this study was designed by considering children's developmental characteristics and has a flexible and holistic structure that adapts to the child's individual needs and learning pace during their interaction with music. The model's foundation is the role of music in supporting children's creative thinking, language development, social interaction, and emotional expression skills. Furthermore, ensuring active family participation in education was emphasized as a key element that enhances the model's success. Including families in the process ensures the continuity and permanence of education by ensuring that children's interaction with music continues in the home environment. Strategies for developing educators' professional competencies have been integrated to enhance the model's applicability and sustainability.

This model, developed in Turkey for early childhood music education, not only supports children's multifaceted development through music but also actively engages families and educators, signaling a significant paradigm shift in terms of quality and continuity in education. Pilot testing of the proposed model in the coming years, collection of field data, and further development of the model through scientific evaluations will ensure that early childhood music education in Turkey becomes systematic, accessible, and of high quality.

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